

Practical Application of Fibre Optic Sensors to Engineered Structures for Real-Time, Nondestructive Evaluation Using a Composite Material Patch

E.E. Tapanes and P.L. Rossiter

Centre for Advanced Materials Technology
Monash University
Clayton, Victoria, 3168. Australia.

Presently there is a high demand for sensors which can be incorporated within a structure or component for monitoring internal/external parameters in real-time. This paper reports on the development of a fibre optic Smart Patch for nondestructive, structural integrity monitoring of engineered structures. The fibre optic Smart Patch reported is analogous to the resistive-foil strain gauge but without the drawbacks of an electrical device. Fibre optic sensors were embedded in graphite/epoxy composite coupons and these were bonded to metallic structures in order to perform strain, vibration and structural resonance measurements. The Smart Patch performance is compared with that of conventional strain gauges.

Key Words: Fibre Optic Sensor, Strain Sensor, Sensing Patch, Structural Integrity Monitoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre optic sensors offer a relatively new technology which is gaining much attention. Presently there is a high demand for sensors which can be incorporated within a structure or component for monitoring internal/external parameters in real-time. Optical fibre sensors, in particular, are very promising for this application due to their dielectric properties and their fine size. Their small size is a major advantage as it enables easy and non-intrusive embedding in a variety of host materials. In addition, they are made from a very durable material (ie. silica) that is corrosion resistant, can operate at high temperatures and have a long fatigue life. Furthermore, fibre optic sensors have several clear advantages over existing conventional sensors such as electrical strain gauges and piezo-electrics, the most significant being immunity to EMI.

Engineered structures are usually not monitored in real-time due to the difficulties in connecting conventional sensors to them and because of the limitations of the sensors. This is particularly so when dealing with metallic structures. In the case of structural integrity monitoring, visual and non-destructive evaluation techniques are required at frequent intervals and often prior disassembly is required. This is a very time consuming and costly exercise. An incorporated sensor which continuously monitors structures in real-time and in-situ would provide significant cost savings and increased safety. In particular, fibre optic vibration sensors could warn of varying amplitude, frequency and duration of vibrations or of a change in the fundamental frequency and/or the material damping coefficient of a structure.

Fibre optic sensors have been successfully embedded in a variety of composite materials to detect and measure damage [1], strain and vibration [2, 3], acoustic emission [4] and temperature [5]. To date, however, real-time structural integrity monitoring systems are not commercially available.

Fibre optic sensors are expected to play a major role in the realisation of these systems and the advent of Smart Structures due to their structural compatibility and sensitivity. There are, however, two significant difficulties which need to be resolved before fibre optic sensors are fully utilised in Smart Structures applications. First, nearly all existing structures and a large proportion of future structures are made of materials (ie., metals) which make embedding the sensors difficult or impractical, while surface adhering the bare sensors is unreliable and renders the sensors susceptible to contact damage. Secondly, components with embedded sensors need to be assembled to form the final structure (ie., the wing of a composite material aircraft) but there are significant difficulties in reliably connecting the sensor networks from component to component and maintaining reliability of the connections during operation.

A fibre optic sensing patch [6] overcomes these difficulties; the sensors are incorporated in a compatible material which can be adhered to any surface of the structure. The Smart Patch is analogous to the electrical strain gauge but without the drawbacks. The patch has the added advantage of protecting the sensor from the environment and from contact damage. The host material of the patch has to be carefully selected to suit the environment of application (ie. hot, cold, dry, wet, etc.) The Smart Patch can be configured to any desired shape and size and can be adhered to most surfaces by means of an appropriate adhesive. The performance of the Smart Patch depends on the transfer of the sensed parameter (ie., strain or acoustic emission) from the structure to the patch. Therefore, particular emphasis should be placed on adhesive selection. The location of application of the Smart Patch could be a critical area, an area that is difficult to reach, or an area where existing defects (ie., cracks, corrosion, disbonding, etc.) need to be routinely monitored. The optical cable emerging from the Smart Patch can then simply follow the same path taken by existing electrical cables of the structure to the main CPU.

A highly cost-effective and efficient repair technology for both repair and structural enhancement of aircraft metallic structures has been developed over the past twenty years, based on the use of boron/epoxy composite patches and structural adhesive bonding. [7,8] Boron/epoxy patches or "doubblers" are bonded to the metallic structure over the damage site and these redistribute and transfer loads over larger areas. In addition, the boron/epoxy doublers act to inhibit crack propagation caused by impact, corrosion and fatigue. While the use of boron/epoxy doublers offers many advantages over mechanically fastened repairs and component replacement, they are most often used as temporary repairs and are not utilised over a potentially much longer operational life-span. This is largely due to the unknown state of the structural component underneath the doubler and consequent difficulty in gaining certification by the relevant airworthiness authorities. Incorporating fibre optic sensors in these boron/epoxy doublers, however, would provide continuous and quantitative assessment of the residual strength of the patched surface, as well as providing information on other environmental parameters. It would be impractical, if not impossible, to embed electrical-based sensors in the same doublers. The smart boron/epoxy patch concept should satisfy the latest airframe design and safety standards, as well as aid in accelerating the certification process and provide real-time structural integrity information.

This paper reports on the development of a fibre optic Smart Patch which is aimed at structural integrity monitoring systems. Fibre optic interferometers were embedded in graphite/epoxy composite patches and these were bonded to steel cantilever beams. Strain and vibration measurements were conducted and the results from the Smart Patch compared favourably with those from electrical strain gauges (ESG) and PVDF piezo-electric sensors. The Smart Patch has demonstrated it's capability of monitoring strain and vibration of steel cantilever beams relative to conventional ESG and PVDF sensors.

2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION AND THEORY

2.1. The structure of optical fibres

Optical fibres are dielectric wave guiding devices used to confine and guide light. The majority of optical fibres used in sensing applications have silica glass cores but some special materials, such as sapphire, fluoride glasses and Neodymium doped silica are utilised for specialised applications.

The core is surrounded by a dielectric material called the cladding. The cladding's refractive index must be lower than the core to satisfy Snell's Law for total internal reflection and thus propagation of the light along the fibre core. The cladding is generally made from silica glass, although for some applications a plastic or doped silica cladding is used. A barrier layer of plastic (the "buffer") is used to jacket the fibre; this provides the fibre with mechanical strength and protects it from damage or moisture absorption. **Figure (1)** illustrates a cross-sectional view of an optical fibre.

Figure 1: Cross-sectional view of typical optical fibre.

A simplistic definition of the modes that are guided by an optical fibre can be explained as the locus of all the light rays which are launched at different entry angles into the core of the fibre. For any optical fibre the number of modes that will be guided by the fibre is dependent on core size, the ratio of core/cladding refractive indices, and the wavelength of operation. Depending on the optical property utilised for the sensing application, the number of modes propagated by an optical fibre is an important parameter.

Light that is launched into and confined to the fibre core propagates along the length of the fibre unperturbed unless acted upon by an external influence. Any disturbance of the fibre alters the characteristics of the guided light; such alterations can be monitored, and related to the magnitude of the disturbing influence.

2.2. Capabilities of Fibre Optic Sensors

Fibre optic sensors and systems have proven their capabilities in various applications and environments; for example, optical fibre based systems have demonstrated their capabilities to

- carry million times more data with less distortion and error than copper wires ever could
- detect strains, static and dynamic, more reliably and more accurately than most strain gauges
- measure temperature from -200°C to 1000°C for silica, 1750°C for sapphire fibres with better than 0.1°C resolution possible
- monitor the composition of gases or liquids, with an accuracy approaching parts per billion
- provide immunity to telecommunication networks from electrical interference and radiation
- withstand most mildly corrosive liquids and gases for decades
- be used at any pressure, deep under the sea or in space, without adjustment
- be used in very confined spaces such as living veins and airways, without discomfort.

2.3. Sensing Techniques

A Michelson fibre optic sensor [2] was used for strain measurements while a novel modal interferometric sensor was used for vibration monitoring. The advantages of these sensors is their high sensitivity and their non-destructive operation, ie. they do not rely on failure or fracture as is the case with the Hofer and Malek sensor [7]. The sensors utilise the properties and characteristics of the electro-magnetic wave propagating in the fibres to monitor the desired parameters.

2.3.1. Michelson Fibre Optic Sensor

The Michelson fibre optic sensor (MFOS) is analogous to the well-known bulk optic interferometer. [3] A coherent, narrow-band laser beam is injected into the core of a singlemode fibre. A singlemode 3 dB fibre optic coupler is then used to excite both the reference fibre and the signal fibre. The reference and signal fibres are placed adjacent to one another along their entire lengths to provide common-mode rejection. The signal arm is longer than the reference arm and this differential length determines the gauge (sensing) length of the sensor. The ends of the two optical fibres are cleaved and mirrored by a metal deposition technique. The optical radiation propagating along the two arms is back reflected by the mirrored ends and the beams coherently recombine at the coupler. The resultant signal is monitored by a detector on the output-arm of the coupler and is related to the net relative phase difference between the two arms of the MFOS. The phase difference corresponds to the strain in the sensed region.

The transfer function of the MFOS represents a sinusoidal fringe pattern with periodicity of 2π radians which corresponds to an effective change in the sensor gauge length of $\lambda/2$, where λ is the effective wavelength in the optical fibre. The strain induced phase change of the sensor can therefore be monitored by counting fringe shifts relative to a co-located ESG reading. Valis et. al. [2] and Tapanes [3] have thoroughly characterised the MFOS and have found that it consistently yields a linear strain-phase relation ($r^2 > 0.999$) for increasing and decreasing load, that there is no systematic variance between tension and compression and that the sensor sensitivity is independent of the sensor gauge length.

2.3.2 Multimode Fibre Optic Interferometer

Optical fibres were found to be very microphonic quite early in the development of fibre optic sensors. [10] In the simplest configuration, a source of coherent optical radiation is used to launch light into a multimode fibre and a photodetector monitors the transmitted output signal. Vibrations and acoustic signals acting on the multimode fibre causes a change in length, diameter, and refractive index of the waveguide, resulting in phase and polarisation modulation of the individual modes supported by the fibre. Each mode is modulated differently and therefore travels through a different path to the end-face of the fibre. The transmitted modes in the fibre combine or interfere at the fibre end-face and the pattern is received by the detector. The observed interference pattern is in the form of a chaotically distributed speckle pattern. Any external perturbations acting on the fibre thus randomly redistributes the speckle pattern with a resultant amplitude modulation perceived at the detector. Although this type of sensor is very sensitive, the amplitude modulation is generally nonlinearly related to the phase modulation, resulting in deep fading and drifting of the output signal. This behaviour limits the use of this sensor for quantitative strain measurements, but nonetheless it can be used as a threshold-type sensor.

Ignatyev et. al. [11] have analysed the spatial-temporal coherence function propagation in multimode fibres when propagated by a coherent source of radiation. They found that the spatial-temporal coherence function at the multimode fibre end-face is represented as a sum of stationary and nonstationary terms related to the spatial and temporal coherence properties of the optical signal and waveguide. Summarising their results, they derived that a multimode fibre with a given index profile possesses spatial coherence filtering properties, even for a spatially incoherent source of input radiation. They predicted that the spatial coherence of the radiation that has passed through quite long lengths of multimode fibre (2m to 1000m) is spatially stationary and has a coherence radius (typically 2-3 μm) related to the wavelength and fibre numerical aperture. Therefore the central core region of the multimode fibre end-face with a radius less than or equal to the coherence radius could be considered spatially coherent and stationary. This yields improved linearity in the amplitude modulation resulting in a reduction in signal fading and drifting. [12] A small diameter region of the multimode end-face may be monitored by splicing a singlemode fibre diaphragm to the multimode fibre. [11, 12] The singlemode fibre should be made sufficiently long to attenuate all cladding modes in order to improve the signal to noise ratio (SNR).

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The MFOS and modal interferometers were constructed using all-fibre, connectorised components. A Dynavac Sputter Coater, Model SC150, was used to deposit gold mirrors on the sensing fibre end-faces. The optical signals were analysed and displayed in real-time using an AMLAB digital signal processing (DSP) unit with a fibre optic interface. [13] Figure (2) illustrates the entire experimental configuration.

Figure 2: Experimental Setup

The MFOS was constructed using an MRV-1 100 μW , singlemode pigtailed laser diode operating at $\lambda=1318.5$ nm. The laser diode pigtail was FC-connected to an AOFR 1300 nm singlemode, 3 dB (2X2) fibre optic coupler. MM Cables 1300 nm singlemode fibres with $9/125$ μm core/cladding diameters and mirrored end-faces were mechanically coupled to the two sensor ports of the (2X2) coupler using Dorran mechanical splices. The remaining output port of the coupler was ST-connected to a Lytel 259013 ST-receptacled InGaAs photodiode. The sensor gauge lengths used were typically 8 mm in length.

The modal interferometer was constructed using a Toshiba 9211 300 μW , singlemode pigtailed laser diode operating at $\lambda=670.6$ nm. The laser diode pigtail was FC-connected to an AOFR 633 nm singlemode, 3 dB (2X2) fibre optic coupler. An MM Cables 1300 nm singlemode fibre with $9/125$ μm core/cladding diameter and mirrored end-face was mechanically coupled to one of the sensor ports of the (2X2) coupler using a Dorran mechanical splice. The unused sensor port was fractured to minimise end reflections. The remaining output port of the coupler was ST-connected to a Germanium Power Devices GM4HS ST-receptacled Ge photodiode ($R \approx 0.25$ A/W at 670 nm). 1300 nm singlemode fibre was used as the multimode (approximately 43 modes) sensing fibre and the 633 nm, 3.7 μm core diameter fibre lead of the coupler was used as a diaphragm as well as to deliver and return the optical signals to/from the sensing region. The sensor gauge lengths used were typically 7 cm in length.

A set of unbuffered and uncoated sensing fibres were successfully embedded in composite specimens constructed of six layers of unidirectional (0°)6 Hercules AS4 graphite/epoxy. The

resultant Smart Patches were 50 mm wide by 100 mm long and 0.76 mm thick. Each patch had both types of fibre optic sensors embedded between the first and second plies and the sensors were centrally located. Strain relief was provided for the fibres where they emerged from the patches by a flexible adhesive. The Smart Patches were then adhered to a steel cantilever beam with Ciba Geigy Araldite 24 hour epoxy. Electrical strain gauges (ESG) were adhered to the Smart Patch and PVDF piezo-electric polymer sensors were adhered to the opposite side of the beam using a cyanoacrylate adhesive, co-located with the fibre optic sensors, in order to compare results. The steel beams were placed in a cantilever load frame and deflected. Manual fringe counting was performed by applying a flexural point load on the beam and observing every maximum of the output intensity relative to the co-located ESG reading. Dynamic experiments were performed by deflecting the beam tip and releasing. The modal interferometer signal output (vibration) and frequency response (via a Fast Fourier Transform) were compared with the ESG and PVDF sensor responses.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The PVDF piezo-electric sensors were found to be quite unreliable because the silver conducting coating often disbonded from the polymer. In addition, as the PVDF piezo-electric is a dynamic material it responded very poorly at frequencies less than 5 Hz. Furthermore, the sensitivity of the PVDF sensor was not comparable to the ESG or fibre optic sensors. For these reasons, it was decided to discontinue the use of the PVDF sensors and no results from these sensors will be presented.

The MFOS response curves yielded a linear strain-phase response ($r^2 > 0.996$) for both increasing and decreasing load. This result indicates good bonding of the optical fibres within the composite patch and of the patch to the steel cantilever beam.

The Smart Patch with the embedded modal fibre optic interferometer was interrogated for its dynamic strain response. The data was collected in real-time using the AMLAB DSP unit with a fibre optic interface. The data was also Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysed and displayed in real-time by the AMLAB unit in order to determine the beam's frequency characteristics. In each case the Smart Patch response showed excellent correlation with the ESG response. **Figure (3)** illustrates a typical Smart Patch response to dynamic strain and its FFT spectral output as compared to a co-located ESG response. The results correlate very well. An interesting point in this figure is that the Smart Patch continues to give data after the ESG sensitivity has reached its limit. **Figure (4)** illustrates this point further. From this figure, it is estimated that the Smart Patch provides an additional 300 ms of data after the ESG has cut-out. **Figure (5)** illustrates a case where an increasing load is applied to the cantilever beam for approximately 125 ms, held constant for approximately 175 ms and then released. Again the results show excellent correlation between the fibre optic Smart Patch and the ESG responses. These results indicate that the fibre optic Smart Patch is effective for vibrational analysis of structures.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper illustrates for the first time the use of a fibre optic Smart Patch for real-time, nondestructive structural integrity monitoring applications. Monitoring of static strain, dynamic strain (vibration), and structural resonance was successfully accomplished with the Smart Patch as verified by electrical strain gauges and PVDF piezo-electric sensors.

This paper also illustrates that a reliable and accurate fibre optic method of monitoring the integrity of large structures can be developed for permanent operational basis. Development of such systems should substantially reduce down time and service requirements due to the ability of self-diagnosis when linked-up with a computer. Fibre optic sensors offers a very practical method of creating such systems since they do not significantly disturb the material properties or process environment and they are becoming more affordable.

Figure 3: Smart Patch vibration and frequency response.

Figure 4: Smart Patch extended vibration and frequency response.

Figure 5: Smart Patch vibration and frequency response.

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